
USE AND IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND SOCIAL NETWORKS IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

As the advancement of 21st century libraries tries to use social networking sites and social media skills to provide dynamic library services. Most librarians are trying to make available their resources in digital form to reach the users. The ICT has changed the way information has been stored, retrieved and disseminated by libraries. In this era, libraries are providing electronic access to a wide variety of resources, including indexes, full-text articles and complete journals with back files. Libraries have been moving towards an electronic environment, in which sufficient computers are necessary for patrons to access information. These advances made the ongoing efforts to support the traditional services and processes with electronic versions economically feasible for libraries and their users. This article tries to explain how libraries can exploits social networking sites and social media skills to provide dynamic library services.

Keywords: Social media, libraries, library services, digital library, Internet, ICT.

Introduction:

The academic libraries are the institutions that aim to acquire, store and disseminate information to the patrons. Some tools are used to provide services to this group. Information communication technology is an approach to transmitting ideas or thoughts between one another. Through the use of this technology library services are provided with more effect, with more speed. It saves time for users. Social network are the best platforms to provide all services for the user with more ease. There are many techniques used to communicate to the patrons through the network and web technology is the more useful social environment that should be created. Social networking is an internet-based tool to find and connect with people.

Social Networking websites usually have open membership which means that anyone can become a member. It's a process of building a relationship among a group of people who have a common interest. Social networks allow sharing of videos, links, images, galleries, and invitations to events. Users can leave comments to state that they like it. Social networking structure includes having a profile, friends, blogs, posts and usually something unique to that particular social networking. Several types of social networking sites i.e. Facebook, Orkut, flicker, Twitter, myspace, WhatsApp, blog etc.

Importance of Academic Libraries:

Libraries associated with academic institutions are known to be academic libraries. During the modernization of the academic institutions in 21's century, these libraries have also undergone modernization. The advent of information and communication technology has resulted in reducing the size of academic libraries. It has been possible due to the digitization of information. These types of modern academic libraries have rich potential for the information. Digital and electronic information is available in digitized data / information, which has gradually replaced paper-based records. As the digitized information system in comparison to text-based information systems is getting more and more popular these days. The traditional libraries are becoming hybrid libraries as they are in the process of digitization of their documents and moving toward becoming digital libraries. The Internet has become an unavoidable requirement for every educational institution of higher learning.

Technology and Education:

Information and Communication Technology has transformed the traditional methods of teaching and learning in the classrooms. The goal of an education is to transform students into lifelong learners rather than only passive recipients of the information. This new approach to education is to take the students beyond the traditional textbooks and requires to develop a skills in computer technology, critical thinking and information-seeking behavior. Classroom teaching with ICT methods and digitized libraries are the keys to the success of an education program that promotes these qualities. Librarians are known to society as managers and information experts. It is our

duty as modern-day librarians to represent a professional group that learned to bridge the gap between the traditional methods of teaching, learning and the modern techniques used in the organization, management to retrieve the information.

Meaning of Social Network:

Social media and social networking sites has become the essential parts of our daily life for communicating with each other. Social media in a great way responsible to build our digital reputations. *Social networking tools make it possible for us to be proactive in maintaining, building and protecting our brand and help spread word-of-mouth about our books. Social networking is very informative and entertaining and it also aware of various situations or events which are going on in society or the world at large (Paul, Kumarjit. 2014, p.53-55).* Social networking facilitates us to enhance our viewpoints as it enables us for interactive learning activities also. Social networking is a platform where our creations and thoughts are presented to the masses.

Social networking is an online platform or site that focuses on building social relations among people who share common interests and activities. Social networking often involves grouping or communicating specific individuals or organizations together. Social networks provide quick, low-tech methods to generate and maintain web-based subject guides and act as communication tools to enable social interaction among LIS Professionals and patrons. Most social networking services are web-based and provides means for users to interact with each other. The patrons interact, share and exchange resources via social networks and media. It promotes free flow of

information and sharing of resources beyond boundaries.

Social Media Networking and Learning:

The ICT and social networking literate librarians are capable of disseminating the ICT skills to library patrons and peers. This includes guiding and training patrons through social networking sites. They can be communicated how to use resources and tools, teaching about the use of social networking sites for scholarly purposes. They can also convey the faculty and instructors their role in disseminating the information on social networking sites and considerations for issues affecting their students' work.

Social networking sites are extremely popular across age groups and are central forums for accessing and sharing information. LIS Professionals are responding to the popularity of social networking sites and their expanding role in the creation, use, and sharing of information. They engage them as a central medium for interaction with library patrons and providing services to meet their information needs. LIS professionals needs a new branch of skill sets especially in this digital environment specific to utilizing social networking sites to provide quality services and maintain their role as information experts.

The following competencies are required set of skills that LIS professionals should possess as social networking literate information professionals. He must be able to implement library services and utilize information within social networking sites. These include skills for interacting with patrons, understanding and articulating the nature of social networking sites and their potential roles related to library services. The skill sets

also includes creating, presenting content, evaluating and applying information and having the ability to assist patrons for gaining and applying these skills.

LIS Professionals possessing these skills are capable of efficiently and effectively navigating online social networking sites and applying their expertise to services that are to be provided to their users.

Possible implication of Social Networking Tools in Academic Libraries:

Academic librarians can apply social networking tools to share information with teachers, research scholars and students in the easiest way possible in the academic library environment.

The following are three broad categories of social networking tools that can be used to offer services to the users in library and information systems:

A. Networking Tools for Communication:

Through these kinds of tools, academic librarians can be in constant touch with faculty, students and research scholars in the online environment for effective dissemination of information such as CAS and SDI services.

B. Networking Tools for distribution of knowledge:

Providing the right information at the right time in the right way to the right person is the priority of librarians. Information dissemination and sharing is the heart of library services. LIS professionals need to be abreast of all available channels for effective and efficient information distribution in an online environment.

C. Networking Tools for Knowledge Organization:

Knowledge organization environment for getting helpful information which can be accessed with the social networking technologies. The below-mentioned tools are effective in the library and information centre for users.

Benefits of Social Networks in Academic Libraries:

1. Social networking / Media technology gives us access to easy, instant communication tools.
2. Social networking gives you a chance to connect with people around the world.
3. Social networking helps people who are soft spoken or socially isolated to connect with others.
4. Social networking gives users immediate access to their teaching updates.
5. Social networking refines strategies.
6. Social networking improve innovation in teaching and learning.
7. Social networking develops communicative skills along with social rapport.
8. Social networking media allow users to quickly share their academic tasks.

Advantages of Academic LIS Professionals:

1. Social media is a easiest tool to market your library services.
2. Social media capture potential users of the library.
3. Social media helps students to use the library services remotely.

4. Social media allows users to create, converse, contribute and share information.
5. It helps libraries to get closer to the users.
6. It helps libraries in building collaborative networks with the users.
7. It is a great way to grab the attention of new users.
8. Social media helps students in locating library resources.
9. Social media facilitates knowledge sharing.
10. Social media helps to feed users with information.
11. Social media helps in promoting distance learning.

Some of the Disadvantages of Social media Networks:

1. Too many social media tools that create chaos.
2. Waste of too much time to use social media.
3. Loss of privacy and identity.
4. Loss of confidentiality of information.
5. Lack of knowledge for using the information sources.
6. Inadequate funding for libraries
7. Low interest of some of the librarians and staff in learning and utilizing social media
8. Inadequate training opportunities for library staff.
9. Electricity failure.
10. Slow speed of the Internet.
11. Issues of copyrights for digital content.

Application of Web 2.0 and 3.0:

Web 2.0, also known as Library 2.0, is user centred web, where blogs, wikis, social networks, multimedia

applications, and dynamic programming scripts are being used for collection, contribution and collaboration on the web. The underlying principle is 'share the resources collectively'. The application of web 2.0 in libraries has taken libraries into a new generation. The librarians need to experience web 2.0 tools from a user's perspective and use these tools in modernizing library services. Web 3.0, also known as semantic web, is smarter and can understand what you want.

Recommendations:

Based on the results of this study provides the following recommendations:

1. Keeping in view the importance of social networking and social media for marketing libraries among internet users, service must be provided in all types of libraries to utilize social media tools.
2. All libraries should develop their website, blogs, and web pages.
3. Libraries should create their social media marketing plan and social media services.
4. In a competitive environment, libraries should employ social media to communicate the library's mission.
5. It is recommended that libraries should provide their patrons with tools for accessing social media by developing social media pages on the library website.
6. Facebook is much popular among teens; it is recommended that libraries should develop their Facebook pages on their websites.
7. Librarians must be educated and trained in using social media tools for marketing library resources and services.

8. Library associations, alumnae and LIS schools should play their role in popularizing the use of social media among LIS professionals.
9. All the Syllabi in bachelor and Master of Library Science should emphasize the practical aspects of marketing and using social media for this purpose.
10. Future research should be conducted to investigate the use of different social media among students and the general public.

Conclusion:

Role of librarian in modern internet community Web World Web 2.0 emphasizes a guide for information rather than the traditional role of an information keeper. The Technological era has already begun and we and the library professionals have to express our identity by acquiring the requisite knowledge and skills and providing the right information to the user at the right time, which has been our motto ever since. The expectations of social media in Academic libraries have very high in the library field, and much advocated in Library 2.0 literature and using various Social Media Networks. In this context, sufficient training and more expertise need to be gained by him to furnish an absolute shape to social networks in the library.

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